

RRING T4.3.4 Codebook

RRING Project subtask 4.3.4: Thematic focus analysis on the role of gender (RRI key) and diversity/inclusion (AIRR) across the 4 key domains, 5 UNESCO regions and different stakeholder types

This document, 'RRING T4.3.4 Codebook', supports the thematic focus analysis subtask 4.3.4 in Task 4.3 (T4.3) under Work Package (WP) 4 (*Global comparative analysis of the RRI State of the Art*), in the EU Horizon 2020 project: *Responsible Research and Innovation Networking Globally (RRING)*. The overarching project aim is to bring Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) into the linked up global world to promote mutual learning and collaboration in RRI. The scope of work in subtask 4.3.4 involves a comparative analysis identifying key RRI players, leaders and networks globally, which are relevant to gender, diversity and inclusion. It also includes policy drivers and focus areas, terminology, and both the short- and medium-term horizon. This comparative analysis includes:

- In-depth comparative analysis across the 4 key domains focusing specifically on this theme.
- A theme-specific comparative analysis (high level) across the geographies, for all RPOs and RFOs.
- A theme-specific consideration of what the RRING research data show about the “linked up global” extent for RRI policy and practice, role of nation-states and international organizations in this global world of RRI in the context of gender, diversity and inclusion.

The development of this codebook (*using an inductive approach and supplemented with key concepts deductively developed from the literature to address the scope of this subtask*) was specified in the WP4 guideline and T4.3.4 action plan.

This document sets out seventeen (17) codes (*an integration of codes deductively developed from the literature with those inductively identified from the textual data - reflecting RRI key and AIRR dimensions*), their descriptions and examples from the transcripts to illustrate the meanings.

To develop the inductive codes, an open coding approach and qualitative line-by-line coding process¹ was used to identify initial codes from the textual data sources – transcripts from WP3 (*qualitative survey and interview*) and WP5 (*case study interviews – T5.2 and T5.4*). The inductive coding process focused specifically on the survey/interview items that addressed the theme of gender equality (*RRI key*), diversity, inclusion, intersectionality and AIRR dimensions. Open coding involves labelling concepts, defining and developing themes/categories based on their properties and dimensions. This coding approach underscores the main objective of the qualitative interview/survey of gaining a ‘bottom-up’ perspective on RRI that reveals local policies, practices and processes that are employed globally towards ensuring that research and innovation are ethical, socially inclusive and addresses public concerns. Ten percent (10%) of the transcripts in the respective work packages was selected as sample for coding using stratified random sampling method². The deductive codes were developed from the literature in anticipation of the emergence of possible codes relating primarily to the AIRR dimension, other diversity dimensions (not explicitly referred to in the data collection instruments) and commonly applied concepts of gender, diversity and inclusion³. Rivas (2012)⁴ suggests that researchers may deductively derive codes from previous research or theoretical literature, or experience or intuition of the researchers. Deductive codes used for the development of this codebook derived mainly from the literature. For instance, the development of the AIRR dimensions emerged through consulting Burget et al. (2017)⁵ and Ludwig and

¹ Corbin, J. and Strauss, A. (2015) *Basics of qualitative research: techniques and procedures for developing grounded theory*. 4th edition. London: SAGE

² Cochran, W. G. (1977) *Sampling techniques*. 3rd edition. New York: Wiley.

³ European institute for gender equality (EIGE) (<https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/concepts-and-definitions>)

⁴ Rivas, C. (2012) Coding and analysing qualitative data. *Researching society and culture* 3, 367-392

⁵ Burget, M., Bardone, E. and Pedaste, M. (2017) Definitions and conceptual dimensions of responsible research and innovation: A literature review. *Science and engineering ethics* 23 (1), 1-19.

Macnaghten (2020)⁶. Codes relating to other diversity dimensions and gender and diversity concepts were derived from the European institute for gender equality. The deductively derived codes may be refined or adjusted inductively as the analysis progresses.

In WP3 sample, qualitative survey items: *Questions 2, 3 and 15*, and interview items: *Questions 7, 7a, 7b and 9*, were analysed and coded. Sample transcripts from WP5 were analysed and coded using the survey/interview-specific questions and thematic categories: gender equality (RRI key), diversity, inclusion and AIRR dimensions (*as pre-specified in the guideline*). Qualitative line-by-line coding was performed on all the selected transcripts. The codes were then integrated, defined and thematically organised. To promote rigour the codebook was reviewed by all four UniBRAD team members and was distributed to other RRING project partners (*assigned reviewers*) for further review and validation. Based on the feedback from the assigned reviewers, some primary codes were reorganised as subcodes and similar codes were integrated as appropriate to consolidate meaning and explanation.

The codebooks used in WP3 (*T3.3 Survey – Qualitative Analysis Codebook*) and WP5 were also consulted towards defining the structure of codebook T4.3.4. This codebook will be useful in coding the rest of the transcripts from WP3 and WP5 (using NVivo software to manage the coding process) as well as content analysis of data and writing of findings.

⁶ Ludwig, D. and Macnaghten, P. (2020) Traditional ecological knowledge in innovation governance: a framework for responsible and just innovation. *Journal of Responsible Innovation* 7 (1), 26-44.

Name	Description	Example(s)
1. Definition or explanation of gender equality, diversity, and inclusion	This involves any attempt to define, clarify, explain, or acknowledge the importance of gender equality, diversity, and inclusion. This also includes any reference to or reflection on cultural differences in the application of gender equality, diversity and inclusion, description of gender roles, social or societal expectations and religious context of gender equality.	
a. Conceptual explanations	Any attempt to define, explain or describe the concepts of gender equality, diversity, and inclusion. This includes personal choice of terms, explanation or clarification of what the terms mean.	<p>More than "gender equality" I prefer "gender balance", or at any case "gender opportunity equality" (Q5GE1571)</p> <p>Actually, we tend to focus on gender equity rather than gender equality, although both are of interest. (Q4GEDG51)</p>
b. Contextual explanations	Any attempt to provide contextual explanation or clarification of the concepts of gender equality, diversity, and inclusion. This could either be cultural, religious or national perspectives.	<p>I wouldn't have a clue the the you could have put that question into the context of the country in which it is asked, Botswana is a very patriarchal system. It's run by men,` with women, having some senior roles, but primarily the senior roles in government in the administration , the university and researchers are mostly men. So I think that's just a cultural issue. It's not to say that women aren't good researchers. We've got some very good women researchers here. But historically, Botswana has been run by men. So I think I think men get on okay with men. I think men get okay with women. But perhaps it haven't been given the opportunity. Women haven't been given the opportunities that men have. (BW02)</p>
c. Importance of gender equality, diversity and inclusion	This is when respondents acknowledge that there are derivable benefits from gender equality, diversity and inclusion. This could involve mentioning identified	<p>At present I'm organising an event with my French partners. We are inviting a person who created an artificial arm. We might invite Paralympic athletes or people who are in a wheelchair.</p>

	benefits such as improvements in innovation and decision-making. Also, code here when respondents merely acknowledge the importance of the question or say the concepts of gender equality, diversity and inclusion are important in their industry or organisation or in wider society.	Having those people as a panellists or discussant is important. They are the users. We have that kind of perspective when we organise that event or create a community. (J2)
2. Country, national or cultural comparisons or perspective of gender equality, diversity and inclusion	Any effort to compare gender equality and diversity practices, legislative frameworks or perspectives of one country or culture with another. This includes explaining the differences and similarities in a country or society with another.	Europe is doing a lot, that it is pushing for a whole series of directives that have been adopted and on the Court of Justice's sentences. These factors push more and more to ensure that companies respect this balance both for remuneration and participation in occupational activities within companies. But, in Italy, the path is particularly uphill precisely due to the type of work on site, which is a job that has had a very masculine image, even if the digital and technological evolution (I03) I think you have mostly answered the following question about culture, specifically Japanese culture as it pertains to gender. Japan is often described as a male-dominated society, especially in science and technology. (5.4.18)
3. Policies or lack of policies on gender equality, diversity and inclusion at international and national levels	This includes mentions, explanations or reflections on policies (strategies, initiatives, interventions, practices) at the international or national governmental levels. It also includes constraints to policy implementation or critique of available policies, norms and activities designed to promote gender equality, diversity and inclusion.	
a. International legislations/policies on gender equality, diversity and inclusion	This involves any reference to adherence to international laws or policies such as those by EU, UN, NATO, AU, ECOWAS etc. in relation to gender equality, diversity and inclusion.	signed up to provisions of (...) and EU policies on gender balance and equality. (Q152D8DE)

		Europe is doing a lot, that it is pushing for a whole series of directives that have been adopted and on the Court of Justice's sentences. These factors push more and more to ensure that companies respect this balance both for remuneration and participation in occupational activities within companies. (I03)
b. National Government policies or legislations or interventions on gender equality, diversity and inclusion	Any reference to specific government policies, Acts, initiatives etc. on gender equality, diversity and inclusion (including attempts at explaining such laws even when not explicitly mentioned).	Government always talks about employment, gender equality, poverty eradication, and so but there's nothing to stop those things happening. (BW02) however there are some initiatives from the government as to encourage women for example . (EG05)
c. Lack of or uncertainty of government policies or legislation on gender equality, diversity and inclusion	Code here when respondents show a lack of knowledge, awareness or explicitly state that there are no government policies, legislation, or initiatives on gender equality, diversity and inclusion.but there are no policies that encourage the inclusion of minority groups. (BO01) No. No, and also because of the current political environment. For example, the episode recently occurred with the advertisement of Banco do Brasil. The federal government is my boss, and the message given is clear. This is not the best time to inclusive projects. Our actions are tied to the executive branch, and although the actions are available on our site, I do not have confidence that any public policies will support me in this sense. (BR04) I do not know explicit policies to promote women participation in the mining sector. (BO01)
d. Constraint to the implementation of national government policies on gender equality, diversity and inclusion	References to or mentions of factors impeding the implementation of government policies. These could be a lack or inadequacies in the supporting structures to enhance successful implementation such as poor	

	funding, lack of enforcement mechanisms, ambiguity in legal provisions etc.	
4. Institutional/Organisational policies, practices or initiatives on gender equality, diversity and inclusion	This includes explicit mentions of organisational strategies, initiatives, interventions, and practices not covered by the sub-code identified below.	Our organisation has a Diversity Steering committee, clear aims and ambitions and proactive involvement (implicit bias training for HR and senior management, Female Leadership Training) etc. (Q4G814EE)
a. Fairness/Equality/Equity/Non-discrimination	Any implicit or explicit reference to organisational practices as being fair or devoid of any form of discrimination.	<p>I've already answered that I mean the as I said, we have what do we have we have normal practices, we don't have discrimination , that the the best person for the job is appointed to the job. So we abide by the rules of non discrimination by gender or ethnicity or whatever. So there's nothing to stop diversity in a field. (BW02)</p> <p>In my company I take care of number if male and female employees to be in balance. They have same salaries and other conditions (Q86GE242)</p> <p>So we abide by the rules of non-discrimination by gender or ethnicity or whatever. (BW02)</p>
b. Identity-blind organisational practices or policies or meritocratic policies	Any reference to not using gender and ethnicity as identifiers in employment process, promotion, training, team selection, and work allocation, committee selection, admission of students, panel selection, and other human resource activities. It also includes reference to selection based on competence, merit, capability, qualification, ability, knowledge or being right for the job, physical or mental suitability for the position and not based on any diversity consideration. Also, code here when there is reference to equal opportunity employment.	We're really trying to be at the forefront of hiring practices, for example, in our most recent round of hiring, we had a completely blind assessment process. The hiring manager wasn't given a name or any identifiable information. They were given an assessment for the task. They assessed that and then only once they decided right here are the people that we want to invite to interview, only at that point were they given any information about, for example, the gender or their nationality. (5.4.15)

		<p>New PhD students have been selected in the last 12 months and the decision was based entirely upon their own merit and not that of their preferred gender. (Q6GEE561)</p> <p>Appoint team members if found competent. (Q6GEE494)</p> <p>It's a, when we appoint researchers, we appoint on merit without a point on gender, or whatever we, we say, who's the best person for the job. And if it's a man than the man gets the job, if it's a woman, the woman gets the job. (BW02)</p>
c. Diversity statement, messaging, language and symbols in internal/external communication	Code here when there is explicit or implicit reference to diversity embedded in messages, language, symbols, position statements used in internal/external communication such as job adverts, call for papers, abstracts or tenders, conference calls etc. stating an organisation's stance on gender equality, diversity and inclusion.	Diversity statements included in job postings. (Q6GE2728)
d. Sensitization and training events	Any reference to participating in or organising conferences, workshops, symposiums, training, lectures, seminars and other events aimed at discussing or creating awareness or sensitizing the public or participants on gender equality, diversity and inclusion.	<p>(...) conduct internal workshops on ethnic's, unbias training etc. (Q6G628E8)</p> <p>I have conducted a series of gender pedagogy workshops and participate in a gender pedagogy working group at the university. (Q78E912D)</p>
e. Gender equality and diversity consideration in the employment cycle	Here there is a consideration for gender equality and diversity in the employment cycle: attraction, recruitment, selection, progression, promotion or any other human-resource-related activity. This includes affirmative or positive action measures in institutions or countries. This can also be simultaneously coded under organisational or governmental policies on gender equality and diversity.	Yes. I agree it's difficult in the social structure from where we come, but we have been making sure that at the starting level itself, for the graduates that we induct, we ensure that there is a healthy percentage of the gender diversity, so that by the time people learn over the years, then they are ready to immediately take up the leadership roles. From five years, seven years in the company, we start ensuring that people start taking lead roles. That's how when you train a lot of gender

		diversity within the company, then you grow the talent also. It's a part of the initiative from the grassroots level itself. (5.2.4)
f. Hiring/representation/inclusion of women and girls	Any reference to hiring/employment, inclusion or representation of women, females or girls in any role without explicit mention of gender balance and inclusion, to reflect that women are not excluded in an industry, organisation or team. This includes hiring into junior roles. It can also be simultaneously coded into "women in junior roles".	I have hired 2 female research assistants (Q78E912D) And, then, we obviously have a very important technical scientific dimension and that is connected to the action that is being carried out to increase the female presence (I03)
g. Membership of gender equality or diversity and inclusion committee	Any reference to membership of a gender equality or diversity and inclusion committee in an organisation. This also includes being a diversity champion or one who drives the gender equality, diversity and inclusion agenda in an organisation or for the government.	
h. Gender equality and Diversity – not an issue/Inclusion achieved	Any reference to gender equality, diversity and inclusion not being an issue in an organisation. This includes reference to having a diverse team or organisational composition, gender equality in collaboration with students and community members. Code here also for reference to fairness in human resource policies and practices.	The team consists of members with high cultural heterogeneity. Both culturally and in terms of phenotype, the team has a great diversity (Q15929E2)
i. Mentorship, encouragement, support, assistance and advice for women and other minorities	This includes references to mentorship, encouragement, or advice given to people of minority gender, ethnicity or other diversity dimensions to support their work, encourage their participation in certain fields or to advance their career. It also includes helping female colleagues or ethnic minorities make applications for admission or research funding.	encourage female colleagues, help them with applications; (Q2D15528) active encouragement and support for minority-background scholars and professionals; including support for refugee scholars (Q2D16G76)

<p>j. Lack of or uncertainty of institutional/organisational policies or legislation on gender equality, diversity and inclusion</p>	<p>Any reference to uncertainty or lack of institutional policies on gender equality, diversity and inclusion.</p>	<p>I know there is no institutional policy (MO07)</p>
<p>k. Partnerships or collaboration with civil society organisations in promoting gender equality, diversity and inclusion</p>	<p>Partnerships or collaborations with NGOs, foundations, civil society organisations or pressure groups in the promotion or advancement of gender equality, diversity and inclusion.</p>	<p>but also with NGOs working with people with the HIV virus, among others. We also have initiatives related to the development of women's professional careers. What I would highlight is the adherence of these groups, who really engage and perceive this inclusion deeply. (BR04)</p>
<p>5. Nature of industry, sector, profession, or discipline</p>	<p>Any reference to the nature or peculiarities of industry, organisation or sector of an economy that makes it difficult or unsuitable for gender equality, diversity, and inclusion policies/principles to be applied. This also includes mentions of gender equality and diversity not applicable or relevant in the industry. This could be as a result of the feminine or masculine nature the work performed.</p>	<p>Certainly, gender issues are important especially in sectors like ours. There has been a study in the United Kingdom in which construction is absolutely the last sector in terms of gender equality. Only 1% of workers are not men and, therefore, it is a particularly exposed sector. It has also been highlighted by this study that this entails many problems for the development of the sector, also because then it is proved by an ever-increasing number of studies that instead, the presence of women within the board, within the organizations tends to improve the overall quality of work because obviously excellence is not distributed by gender. (I03)</p> <p>I feel that gender and ethnicity shouldn't be factors in my field in terms of assembling research teams. (Q6GEE561)</p> <p>The mining sector does not encourage the participation of women. (BO01)</p>
<p>a. Female dominance</p>	<p>Any reference to female dominance in an industry, profession, organisation or sector of an economy .</p>	<p>The majority of the people in my research group are women. (QE527DDD)</p>
<p>b. Male dominance</p>	<p>Any reference to male dominance in an industry, profession, organisation or sector of the economy.</p>	<p>Only 1% of workers are not men and, therefore, it is a particularly exposed sector. (I03)</p>

6. Gender representation	Any reference to representation of both women and men within the workplace or society. This also includes emphasis on women holding either senior or junior positions	
a. Equal representation of women and men (50-50)	Any explicit mention of the term 'gender balance' or reference to an equal number of men and women (50-50).	So, the gender balance has ended up roughly in balance, unexpectedly. It wasn't intentional, but it's essentially the situation. (5.4.18) We always try to have an equal number of men & women in all our activities (Q1526E6D)
b. Representation of both women and men in any other proportion	Gender representation in reference to involvement, employment, or mentorship of both women and men or girls and boys or females and males. This also includes numerical reference to the number of women and men in any proportion or percentage but not equal number.	Where possible I make efforts to ensure that both genders are represented in activities such as awareness events, speaker opportunities, case studies etc. (Q2D679G9)
c. Women in leadership or managerial positions	Any reference to women holding senior management or leadership positions to show that they are not excluded in an organisation or country (or in politics). This includes leadership of teams, committees, and other supervisory roles.	There are women who are chairpersons, and it's a normal thing. (5.4.18) The more responsible positions are occupied mostly by women. (Q15929E2)
d. Women in junior roles	Any reference to women in junior roles such as research assistants, interns and other junior administrative positions or positions implicitly considered as lower than those occupied by their male counterparts.	I have hired 2 female research assistants while hiring a male project coordinator (Q78E912D)
7. Gender equality and the creation of social value	Any reference to the influence of gender equality in the creation of social or societal values. For example business related values like competitiveness and ethics.	Q: It's asking whether there may be societal benefit from including not just the points of view of men, but of women, and those with other gender identities, in your kind of work. Int: I can't imagine such benefits. (5.4.18)

<p>8. Personal ascriptions - interviewee's positioning/status</p>	<p>Any reference to interviewee's own gender or ethnic minority status to suggest inclusion. This includes personal principles and values or actions taken on own accord with respect to gender equality, diversity and inclusion. Also code one of the option below when respondents rather give personal advice on what should be done.</p>	
<p>a. I am a woman</p>	<p>Any reference to the respondent's gender as a woman working in a particular industry/field to depict inclusion or absence of discrimination.</p>	<p>I am myself a woman and bring a feminist perspective to my work, sometimes explicitly. (Q4G86159)</p>
<p>b. I am from a minority Ethnic group</p>	<p>Code here when a respondent identifies as a member of an ethnic minority group.</p>	<p>I am one of the ethnic minorities and I tried to be as active as I can in various groups on campus (Q1522546)</p>
<p>c. Personal values / practices / actions taken or advice on what should be done</p>	<p>Any reference to personal principles, values or actions taken on own accord with respect to gender equality, diversity and inclusion. This also includes when the respondent gives a personal opinion on what should be done to enhance gender equality, diversity and inclusion instead of what has been done or what is currently being done.</p>	<p>I don't discriminate against any gender to do so would be counterproductive and illogical (Q2D679G9)</p> <p>I don't discriminate. Whoever comes is welcome, if she or he has the ability and the will ... I had a male post-doc who was an Israeli Arab and he is now faculty at university of Connecticut. (IL04)</p> <p>We should try to live above cast and creed. (Q6GEGE6G)</p>
<p>9. Barriers to gender equality, diversity and inclusion</p>	<p>Any reference to impediments to the inclusion, progress or success of women, people of ethnic minority backgrounds and those with other protected characteristics in employment, education and other aspects of life. This only covers barriers relating to cultural practices, domestic responsibilities, pregnancy and childcare, societal expectations, religious practices and other gender roles/responsibilities. And not constraints to policy implementation</p>	<p>Japan is often described as a male-dominated society, especially in science and technology. It is generally said, and you have said, that academic women are often expected to care for their children for example, or do other caring roles in the home. (5.4.18)</p> <p>Just recently for a committee on our campus an academic asked about bringing her child to the meetings, because the child was still small. I don't think that's a problem, if the child's security is</p>

		ensured, for example, by her safely holding her child. But because there's no precedent, I told her I would enquire of some suitable person. Do you think that kind of point will come? (5.4.18)
10. Dangers of exclusion or lack of gender equality, diversity and inclusion	Any reference to adverse effects caused by lack of gender equality, diversity and inclusion.	So if one excludes the half, a little more than half of mankind, risks excluding many Marie Curies who could make a big contribution instead. (I03) I don't discriminate against any gender to do so would be counterproductive and illogical (Q2D679G9)
11. Conduct /involvement in research and innovation	Any reference to the involvement of women, people of ethnic minority backgrounds or indigenous groups/ communities in different research capacities, either as researchers, research participants or members of research advisory boards. This also includes participants' mention or description of their own research study on gender, diversity and inclusion, or the involvement of women and other minority groups in their study.	
a. Mention of own/group study on gender equality, diversity, and inclusion	This included references to own/group research work, PhD study or any other study focusing on gender equality, diversity and inclusion. This also includes mentions of the methodological design of the study that specifies the participation of women or people of ethnic minority backgrounds.	setting up a research framework for a religious minority in the community, reading its history and preparing the fieldwork and the interviews. (Q2D15D65) My current research is about cancer screening uptake and ethnicity since there are wide differences in screening uptake. The focus of my research is to work with different ethnic minority groups to find out what the barriers to screening participation are and develop a co-produced culturally appropriate intervention to improve screening uptake. (Q2D62264)

		My PhD thesis and many of my work revolves around gender equality, women's empowerment and family policy (Q5GE7814) participatory methodologies (QD6889D2)
i. Gender equality, diversity and inclusion as dimensions within research	Code here where the researcher considers specific gender equality, diversity and inclusion perspectives within their study.	use of gender neutral language in publications (Q4G88976) I analyze the results from the gender perspective when it is relevant (Q2D6914E)
ii. Gender and ethnic minority as research topic	Any reference to issues of gender and ethnic minority as respondent's research focus/area.	My research has included ethnic minority by design as the research topic addresses their needs over and above enhancing my academic position. (Q4G8568D)
iii. Gender balance in research sample	Code here only for explicit mention of gender balance in research sample or participants or subjects. <i>Note: For generic reference to inclusion of women as research subjects, code "Women involvement in research subjects or sample or participants".</i>	Research subjects involve both gender. My research team has good balance of both females and males. (Q6G67511) By considering the balance of gender in my participants and acknowledging when this balance may not be representative (Q5G967DE)
iv. Ethnic balance in research sample	Code here only for explicit mention of ethnic balance in own research sample or participants or subjects.	Our work focuses on American Indians/Alaska Native reservation based families and their very young children. Our community TRHT work focuses on all members of a community (it a city, it is a representative sample of all ethnic/minority peoples within the city (or region, state, national, etc.) (Q4GE7965)
b. Involvement of women and people of ethnic minority background in research	Any reference to the involvement of women and people of ethnic backgrounds in different aspects of research as highlighted in the sub codes below.	
i. Women as researchers	Any mention of women as researchers.	A pair of women investigators from Argentine exists who are a referring one and the person who knows more on global Lithium markets is a Chilean researcher. But I believe that this

		<p>is more random. The people who are studying the economy of the innovation from a macro point of view are women researchers and like them there are many more people who are interested in the subject. (BO01)</p> <p>Included female researchers and female community members in the process explained above. (Q4G8568D)</p> <p>Request my project partners to include as many as possible female scholars in our research project Q6GE4E51)</p>
ii. Women involvement as research subjects or samples or participants	Any mention of women as research subjects or participants.	identifying the women interviewees and talking to them, (Q2D15D65)
iii. People of ethnic minority backgrounds' involvement as researchers	Any mention of people of ethnic minority backgrounds being involved as researchers.	Invited scholars with minority background to be a research project partner(s). (Q6GE4E51)
iv. People of ethnic minority backgrounds' involvement as research subjects	Any reference to people of ethnic minority backgrounds as research subjects or participant.	<p>By interviewing ethnic minorities in Kenya (Q1524D44)</p> <p>Collecting contrasting views (Majority and Minority) from the people in my research issues (Q1524G96)</p> <p>I am currently working with a minority group (indigenous) by looking at what their needs and matching them with my research and work. (Q95E419G)</p>
v. Gender balance of research advisory boards and other related decision-making bodies	Code here for any reference relating to the composition of research boards and other research decision-making bodies.	gender balance on research advisory groups and bids (Q787D2G4)
c. Women and people of ethnic minority backgrounds as students	This involves reference to women and people of ethnic minority backgrounds being students to convey the fact that they are not completely excluded.	Promote female PhD students (Q2D6285G)

		Have activities with indigenous (students coming from villages) and Maroons (southern Brazil) (Q4G81D91)
d. Gender-based reaction to research and innovation	Any reference to women and men's reaction to research, innovation and technological advancements. This includes perceptions of artificial intelligence, genetical modified organisms/foods, Stem cell research, and gene editing.	<p>...based on the results of a survey in awareness, there is data on how safe they think it is. Although there are no official statistics about genome editing, women are about 30% more likely to feel that it is dangerous, compared to men. (5.4.18)</p> <p>About half of people are anxious that genetically modified foods are somewhat dangerous. But it is around 60% for women and 40% for men. (5.4.18)</p> <p>Q: I have researched implantable electronic devices and brain chips, and have also found women feel more anxious. Int: Yes, it seems true that women feel more anxious about such things generally. (5.4.18)</p>
e. Communities/indigenous involvement in research and innovation	Any reference to inclusion, involvement or consultation of a community or indigenous people in the design and execution of any project.	<p>I am currently working with a minority group (indigenous) by looking at what their needs and matching them with my research and work. (Q95E419G)</p> <p>Have activities with indigenous (students coming from villages) and Maroons (southern Brazil), African-based religion of people with both guidance and integration in the community. They have been instrumental in the design of I develop Cosmocena Ecology and in my research on environmental ontoepistemologia. (Q4G81D91)</p> <p>Working with indigenous communities to create research questions. Ensuring research team has indigenous people who help to lead research and keen non-ethnic minorities safe Making sure research has direct oversight throughout to ensure the research leads to transformative outcomes. (Q86E52E9)</p>

12. Gender equality and diversity concepts	Any reference to or explicit mention of the concepts listed below.	
a. Gender, racial, or intersectional bias	Any reference to prejudice, actions or bias due to gender, race or the combination of gender with other factors, such as sex, race, colour, language, religion, political or other opinions, national or social origin, association with a national minority, property, birth or another status.	Racial bias and gender bias as well. We find that a lot of the existing algorithms work very well for white men and not very well for the majority of our beneficiaries who are women of color basically (5.4.15)
b. Gender discrimination	Any distinction, exclusion or restriction made on the basis of sex which has the effect or purpose of impairing or nullifying the recognition, enjoyment or exercise by women, irrespective of their marital status, on the basis of equality of men and women, of human rights and fundamental freedoms in the political, economic, social, cultural, civil or any other field.	Some critics had that reaction, but I was sad to see that Japanese male students were saying “what the hell is this kind of woman saying?” (J02)
c. Gender pay gap	Any reference to differences in remuneration or financial benefits between women and men performing similar jobs. This also includes specific mention of gender pay gap or equal pay.	It’s a very, very good point. We fall below the threshold at which we’re legally required to report the gender pay gap. In the UK there’s above a certain number of employees you have to report gender pay gap data. (5.4.15)
d. Gender mainstreaming	Any reference to ensuring that women’s and men’s concerns, needs and experiences are fully considered in the design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of all activities.	supported researchers on how to mainstream gender equality into their research proposals and practice (Q15874D7)
e. Women empowerment	Any reference to women empowerment. To be empowered women and girls must not only have equal capabilities (such as education and health) and equal access to resources and opportunities (such as land and	Women empowerment is truly represented in Dayalbagh at all levels (Q6GEGE6G)

	employment), but they must also have the agency to use these rights, capabilities, resources and opportunities to make strategic choices and decisions (such as is provided through leadership opportunities and participation in political institutions).	
f. Affirmative Action	Any explicit mention of the term 'affirmative action', positive action, 'positive discrimination' or 'reversed discrimination' and quota.	I guess there are times when there is a demand for the same number of men and women to appear as a form of affirmative action. (5.4.18) Working with affirmative action at the University integrate to participate in the municipal conference in Rio Grande (Q4G81D91)
g. Microaggression	Any reference to brief and commonplace verbal, behavioural, and environmental indignities whether intentional or unintentional, that communicate hostile, derogatory, or negative racial, gender, and sexual orientation, and religious slights and insults that target person or group.	
h. Unconscious/Implicit bias	Code here where there is a reference to prejudice, bias or social stereotypes about certain people or groups of people that the respondent holds (usually in a way that is considered to be unfair) outside her/his own conscious awareness.	We found this was really useful, in terms of really trying to stand part of that unconscious bias, there's a lot of research which says the unconscious bias training doesn't really work. It doesn't really do anything, so actually it's much better rather than train people on unconscious bias, it's much better to actually just remove the chance of bias as far as you can. (5.4.15)
i. Intersectional discrimination	Code here where there is a specific reference to discrimination that takes place on the basis of several personal grounds or characteristics/identities, which	

	operate and interact with each other at the same time in such a way as to be inseparable.	
13. Other diversity dimensions	Any reference to other diversity dimensions as listed below.	
a. Race / mixed racial heritage	Any reference to diversity and inclusion in R&I/workplace in terms of race / mixed racial heritage.	promoted my research as a resource to institutionalising race equality in World Technology Higher Education Institutions (Q15874D7)
b. Age	Any reference to diversity and inclusion in R&I/workplace in terms of age group, seniority, or generational difference.	I always consider about gender equality and how to bring in younger people. (J02)
c. Religious beliefs	Any reference to diversity and inclusion in R&I/workplace in terms of religious beliefs.	African-based religion of people with both guidance and integration in the community. They have been instrumental in the design of I develop (...) and in my research on environmental ontoepistemologia. (Q4G81D91)
d. Education / Qualification	Any reference to a mix or inclusion of people with different levels of education, qualification or professional affiliation in R&I/workplace.	
e. Language / Accent	Any reference to diversity and inclusion in R&I/workplace in terms of language or accent.	Not all terms and concepts translate well into other languages/cultures. (Q6GE78E7) We have established programmes to develop science communication in indigenous languages. (Q5GE8D2E)
f. Socioeconomic status	Any reference to diversity and inclusion in R&I/workplace in terms of income, class, social status etc.	However, where there is a culture or ethnic characteristic of certain projects it will be highlighted (e.g. as caste study) as an example of the value of diversity (Q2D679G9)
g. Disability / Health status	Any reference to diversity and inclusion in R&I/workplace in terms of health status or any form of disability.	I often use advisory groups and aim to recruit diversity in race, age, gender, disability status, and rural/urban status (Q78E2GD1)

h. Marital status	Any reference to diversity and inclusion in R&I/workplace in terms of marital status – single, married, divorced, widow, or widower.	I do not read such general information (age, sex, religion, race, marital status) of candidates who have to work with me, but only the scientific and academic CV. (Q4G8292D)
i. Parental status	Any reference to diversity and inclusion in R&I/workplace in terms of parental status.	
j. Occupational diversity	Any reference to diversity and inclusion in R&I/workplace in terms of blend of people from different occupations, and profession working together in the same organisation.	These factors push more and more to ensure that companies respect this balance both for remuneration and participation in occupational activities within companies.(Italy)
k. Geographic location	Any reference to diversity and inclusion in R&I/workplace in terms of geographic location.	
l. Sexual orientation	Any reference to diversity and inclusion in R&I/workplace in terms of sexual orientation and preferences. This involves references to lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, transsexual, queer, questioning, intersex, asexual, ally, pansexual and gender variant.	We have developed several projects with LGBT community (BR04) It is a factor closely related to our theme of social innovation. We have developed several projects with LGBT community, but also with NGOs working with people with the HIV virus, among others (BR04)
m. Physical appearance	Any reference to diversity and inclusion in R&I/workplace in terms of physical appearance.	
n. Work experience	Any reference to diversity and inclusion in R&I/workplace in terms of skills and depth of experiences gained in a particular profession.	
o. Nationality	Any reference to diversity and inclusion in R&I/workplace in terms of legal nationality status.	only at that point were they given any information about, for example, the gender or their nationality (5.4.15)
p. Intersectionality	Any reference to the interconnectedness of social categorisations such as race, class, gender and other dimensions as they apply to a given individual or group.	

14. Responding to societal needs	Any reference to research and innovation activities being carried out in response to societal needs concerning women, men, children, indigenous people, refugees, and other ethnic minority groups.	We think it's very relevant to the work and as I mentioned, the five research priority areas for the university, water, food, health, are clearly all involved in in research and innovation, because they speak to the societal needs. And they also speak to the benefits of society, such as employment or gender balance or poverty eradication. So it's, it's very important that we do our research, which is for the benefit of society. (BW02)
15. Impact of research and innovation	Any mention of the impact of research and innovation process or outcome on immediate communities, indigenous people, specific gender or ethnic minority groups.	
a. Anticipation/Consideration of future impact of research and innovation	This involves mentions relating to the anticipation of future impact of research and innovation activities on gender equality, diversity and inclusion as well as societal, political, environmental and technical considerations in the design and implementation stages. It also involves reflecting on the motivations and implications of a research project, being clearer about uncertainties and dilemmas and opening the visions to the broader public. This also includes consideration or anticipation of potential future harm caused by research and innovation to gender categories, members of vulnerable social groups, host communities, less privileged population or ethnic minority population.	
b. Responsiveness	Any reference to the identification of potential gender equality and diversity related risks involved in research and innovation projects and appropriate reactions. The risks involved in new technologies can be medium- or long-term, economic, environmental or societal that	

	<p>have gender-specific impacts or impacts on ethnic minority or indigenous people. Code here where there is a reference to consideration of impacts of research and innovation activities on host communities or less privileged population or indigenous communities or ethnic minority population.</p>	
<p>c. Reflexivity</p>	<p>Any mention of having public dialogue, science and public collaboration in the research and innovation process. It is about “holding a mirror up to one’s activities, commitments and assumptions, being aware of the limits of knowledge and being mindful that a particular framing of an issue may not be universally held”; reflecting on values and beliefs during research and innovation activities. This also includes collaborative approaches by way of public dialogue in the process of research and innovation.</p>	
<p>16. Critiquing or highlighting complexities of gender equality, diversity and inclusion</p>	<p>Any reference to complexities in the practice of gender equality, diversity and inclusion, or personal negative dispositions to the concepts. It also includes critique of the application of gender equality and/or diversity and inclusion as well as critique of the interview or survey questions.</p>	<p>I believe strongly in the need to be conscious of inherent or residual gender and or ethnic bias, but would not implement a policy of positive discrimination in order to artificially create a gender equal, or ethnically balanced research team. (Q152D8DE)</p> <p>So you have a benchmark and you are bringing everybody So what is that benchmark? So you have a benchmark in place that this is the benchmark of rights which would be given to everyone to the benchmark. So if you benchmark someone it means that there is a model whom you see as someone with near to perfect and you benchmark everything to that. When you start benchmarking, you start benchmarking on the pay scale, the way you speak, the way you dress, the way you</p>

		<p>believe, have your beliefs system in place, how you interact among each other in the society. So once you start benchmarking and bringing everybody as equal, you are actually moving away from the concept of diversity. (IND05)</p> <p>This is a little complicated. The region where I work is with where historically (and currently) the people have had fewer opportunities and are generally poorer than the rest of the country. But they are a majority in the region where I work. Still, there are refugees in the region as well, and we try to include opportunities for them where possible as well. (Q78E912D)</p>
<p>17. Vague response or misunderstood questions</p>	<p>Code here when a respondent gives an unintelligible response or gives a completely unrelated response.</p>	<p>Observation, hypothesis, experimental development to evaluate hypotheses, implementation and collection of results, analysis and adjustment of hypotheses. (Q78E586D)</p>